

showed good maintenance, and 7% showed partial restoration. But few showed 60-70% restoration ability. This situation led us to begin a systematic restorer breeding program incorporating ideal Basmati quality.

Testcrosses were made using cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines Pusa 1127A (a new cyto sterility source from Pusa 743), Pusa 3A wild abortive (WA), and IR58025A (WA) with the Basmati cultivar or breeding line that had shown high F_1 fertility (60-70%) in previous testcrosses. All the F_1 s were raised. Seeds from the best fertile plants were harvested and subjected to grain and cooking quality tests. Only those hybrids that exhibited Basmati cooking characteristics in an appreciable proportion of grains were raised to the F_2 generation. Selections were made on the basis of spikelet fertility, grain shape, and grain appearance. They were subjected to cooking quality tests and only those possessing ideal Basmati characteristics were raised to the F_3 . In the F_3 , diverse-looking plants were selectively intermated and the entire process was repeated. Simultaneously, some of these selected plants were testcrossed with Pusa 3A. Pollen donor plants of hybrids showing improved restoration and ideal Basmati quality were advanced to the F_4 . In the F_4 and later generations, the entire process was again repeated as in the F_3 . Likewise, the material was advanced to the F_6 generation. The intermated lines were also advanced to further generations.

Testcrosses made between Pusa 3A and the selected lines revealed that nine lines—Sps95-694-2, Sps95-694-3, Sps95-81-1, Sps95-81-3, Sps95-81-4, Sps95-81-5, Sps95-81-6, Sps95-768, and Sps95-167-1—showed normal restoration. The grain quality of these hybrids was comparable with that of Pusa Basmati 1 and Karnal Local. Three of these lines are now used for Basmati hybrid seed production with Pusa 3A (Basmati CMS line). ■

Genetics of thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

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Understanding the inheritance pattern and studying allelic relations among diverse thermosensitive genic male sterile lines (TGMS) were the objectives of this investigation. Lines F61, SA2, JP1, JP8-8-1s, ID24, and IC10, developed at the DRR, Hyderabad, and lines IR32364, IR68292, IR68294, IR68945, and IR68949, received from IRRI, Philippines, were crossed with a set of normal pollen parents, to study segregation patterns in the F_2 , F_3 , and backcross generations. The results indicated that sterility caused by the TGMS trait was governed by a single recessive gene. In segregating populations, however, individual TGMS progenies from the same F_2 showed different fertility levels. This indicated that some other genes modify the major gene and affect fertility.

Allelic relations were examined by studying direct crosses and backcrosses involving two different TGMS lines over seasons. The lines developed from Norin PL 12 (*tms2*) (IR68292, IR68294, IR68945, and IR68949) at IRRI were allelic to ID24 and JP1. The lines IR32364 (*tms3*), JP8-8-1s, and IC10 were also allelic. Lines SA2 and F61 were observed to be nonallelic to all other lines, and may possess different TGMS genes, including *tms1* from China. ■

Mitochondrial gene expression in cytoplasmic male sterile and fertile lines of rice

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In various plant species, rearrangements in the mitochondrial genome have been associated with cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS). These rearrangements could modify genome expression and thereby play a role in pollen abortion. In rice, investigations carried out in our laboratory have established some rearrangements in the genetic organization of mitochondrial DNA between male sterile and fertile lines. For example, the *cox1* locus was found rearranged in the CMS line compared with the fertile lines.

To establish the correlation, if any, in DNA organizational pattern with the expression of the male sterile phenotype, we conducted a Northern analysis on total RNA from the sterile and fertile lines. The blot, when probed with *atp6*, showed a single transcript in all the lines tested, whereas *atp9* and *cox3 / orf25* showed five and two transcripts, respectively. On probing with *atp9*, we observed multiple transcripts of sizes 3.2 kb, 1.7 kb, 1.3 kb, 0.8 kb, and 0.6 kb, and 0.3 kb was the most abundant of the transcripts, probably representing the mature functional transcript. The cotranscribed genetic locus of *cox3 / orf25* when used as a probe, yielded two transcripts of 2 kb and 1 kb. Even though *atp6* in Chinsurah Boro-type cytoplasm has been found to be differentially transcribed and edited, and hence implicated in CMS, we could not detect different transcripts of *atp6* in the rice lines used in our study bearing WA type cytoplasm. Work on putting more probes on the Northern blots and studying the gene-specific pattern of expression is in progress. ■